

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' READING COMPETENCE WITHIN ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES AT TASHKENT INSTITUTE OF CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract: In this scientific article, correction of the shortcomings in the reading skills of students, development of reading skills, looking at the example of the English language developed. In addition, the methods of developing the reading competence of students of chemical and technological specialties in foreign language learning are analyzed.

Keywords: reading, methodology, oral speech, written speech, rules of speech, language skills, ability.

The higher education in Uzbekistan is currently undergoing significant changes associated with the adoption of new state educational standards, social transformations, scientific and technological modernization. The dynamic development of technology and computerization, the expansion of communication in the field of economics and production, modernization of education system and science are followed by significant changes in social needs of proficiency and competency of modern workers. Furthermore, the growing attention to the social importance of a foreign language in our Republic, the need for experts who know a foreign language is increasing day by day, and in turn, the future chemist-technologists will be able to communicate with foreign partners in their future activities, taking into account the importance of forming the skills of future use of foreign experience in the auditoriums of the institute, our main goal is to give in-depth knowledge to young students, to involve them widely in scientific activities, and to form in them the skills of independent work with foreign literature related to the field. It is of great importance to develop students' receptive skills, which are supportive in dealing with written information about the changes taking place in a proper manner.

Reading is speech related to the perception and understanding of written text receptive type of activity. It is recognition for reading and understanding foreign text phonetic, lexical, and grammatical informational that instantly implements the process is assumed to have a set of properties. Perception and understanding processes are simultaneous and closely related to each other although, the skills that ensure its process are conditionally two divided into groups: related to the "technical" side of reading (perception of graphic symbols) and their connection with certain meanings and what is being perceived ensuring semantic processing - between language units of different levels establishing semantic relations and thus the content of the text, the author's intention and others.

At the initial stage, teaching the student to read correctly, i.e. to sound graphemes, to extract meaning, i.e. to understand text information, it is important to teach how to evaluate and use it. These skills depend on how fast a student learns. Through reading techniques, we not only the quick and clear correlation of sound and letter, but also sound-letter and that the connection is related to the semantic meaning of what the child is reading we understand. Reading is a high level of mastering the reading technique the result of the process itself - allows you to get quick and high-quality information.

The main purpose of teaching "English language" has several components is the formation of communicative competence, which includes:

- communication skills in speaking, listening, reading and writing;
- on the building material of this language for creating and recognizing information language knowledge and skills;
- linguistic and regional knowledge to provide socio-cultural background. It is impossible to form communicative competence without them.

Students learn English as a means of communication and use it in oral and should be able to use in written forms. Interpersonal and International English all forms of communication and all speech to become a means of communication it is very important to master the functions. Four types of student speech activity should master: reading, listening, writing and speaking, as well as with them the advantages of the three aspects of related language - vocabulary, phonetics and grammar should not forget.[1]

Reading in a foreign language requires mastering certain skills of oral and written speech. The teacher should help the student to master the grammatical structure of the studied language, to acquire "secondary language literacy" in constant practice: attach to a new culture, cultural understanding of language and speech, to identify specific formal and content systems. It is important to understand that in order to teach reading in a foreign language, it is literally necessary to change the cognitive activity and the value system of the student. Students should learn to think in a foreign language, and they will be able to read and understand foreign texts effectively. Here, the following recommendations should be taken into account:

➤ Students perceive new things better if they are aware of what they are doing. As soon as they learn the processes of thinking, they begin to monitor their implementation and apply appropriate strategies for understanding the text. L.S. Vygotsky notes that reading is "a very complex mental process. And, first of all, it is important that the work of the visual mechanism here is subordinated to the processes of understanding, and these processes are a very complex ability to establish a relationship between the meanings of words". *It is pointless to teach "reading in general", it should be a conscious process.*

➤ The teacher should encourage students to discuss texts, help them choose strategies for understanding what they read, and give them the opportunity to talk to each other about the meaning. In this case, *students develop grammatical skills.*

➤ Some researchers note that *fluent reading* promotes reflection and improves the understanding of the text.

○ The best way to improve reading is *regularly reading*. By reading, the student expands his vocabulary, grammatical knowledge, the fashion of written and oral speech, improves reading speed, and immerses himself in the culture of the language being studied. [2]

The development of foreign language professional skills of university students is an integral part of education. The university graduates must have a high level of foreign language knowledge in the field of professional work; not only read and translate texts in their specialty, but also develop oral and written communicative skills (resumes, business letters, and other business correspondence) in English at professional level; therefore professional orientation of training requires the integration of a foreign language with relevant disciplines; educational materials should be focused on the

latest achievements in a particular field of activity, reflect scientific discoveries and innovations, relating to the professional interests of students and give them opportunity for professional growth. [3]

In today's rapidly evolving and globalizing information society, it is natural to constantly improve the content of curricula and, if necessary, even radically reform them. The development trend of society corresponds to the improvement of educational processes, that is, knowledge grows dynamically and rises to new qualitative stages. Naturally, these days, when the educational process requires its own complexity, continuous improvement and continuity, educators and scientists have to prepare and reeducate not only the young generation, but all active citizens in society - the socio-political environment in which they live, and consider tactical and strategic tasks aimed at ensuring the implementation of real life requirements and regular updates. [4]

It should be noted that reading texts on specialty at foreign language classes allows students to understand and comprehend specific terms, certain language structures, which contribute to the expansion of student vocabulary with subject terminology and prepares them for further study and application of the knowledge and skills in the field of future professional work.

It is also necessary to read authentic professional oriented texts in the framework of future specialty. Scientific texts differ from other types of texts in both language and structure. They lack a plot and emotional coloring, but there are a large number of special terminologies. During reading authentic professional- oriented texts students increase their ability to identify the necessary information from the proposed material in order to use it further.

Reading is the most interesting thing for a student is one. A student who has learned this skill can easily read a work of fiction in English can also understand. The pinnacle of literacy for the student is this type of skill is known. Learning develops through these games:

1. Who is literate, who is clever;
2. Role-playing game;
3. Find the place of the word;
4. Chain.

Improving student's reading skills while learning a second language will come more naturally and much quicker if you avoid the temptation to constantly re-translate

what you're reading back into your own language. When you're reading in a language that's not your own, it's crucial that you think in that language too. In this sense, reading in a second language is much the same as speaking, writing, and listening in a second language. You're wasting your energy if you're constantly translating what you're reading or hearing back and forth. This is a really important point to consider. When you think in the language you're learning, you're training your mind to function in a bilingual way. This is the crux of how to improve your reading skills in a second language.

Students must have the following knowledge and skills are acquired by systematically:

1. different text types step by step for understanding and discussion (stories, magazine and newspaper articles, news reports, internet texts, etc.) mastering the methods of working with;

2. in order to understand the text different strategies (to understand the main idea reading, reading to get an idea, reading to get special information) acquisition;

3. fiction (short stories and poems in the first year, and novels from the further year) including modern fiction texts be able to read without difficulty and step by step describe the political, able to understand social, spiritual, historical processes;

4. a large text given for reading, understanding and discussion able to work with and draw appropriate conclusions;

5. analysis and discussion based on the opinions and opinions mentioned in the written statements, reports, lectures during the study;

6. relating to different genres and fields, working with dictionaries in some places able to read, understand, analyze and discuss complex texts;

7. different types of texts related to their fields (short stories, magazines, etc.) newspaper articles, news report, internet texts read and related to the text able to draw conclusions;

8. identify thoughts, author's idea and exaggeration in texts;

9. articles on topics related to culture and art (film, theater, fiction) and able to read reviews and say the main points in them;

10. identifying the problems that may be encountered during the study and them liquidation;

11. independent, relying on the information, ideas and thoughts in the given specific texts able to prepare a scientific lecture.

According to the level of penetration into the content of the text and communicative needs there is browsing reading, searching (browsing and searching), accessing and learning. Reading is the correct and complete understanding of the content of the text, the information obtained distinguished by repetition in retelling, synopsis, etc. Reading is the most important part of students' communicative and cognitive activities one of the types. This activity is aimed at obtaining information from a written fixed text. Reading has different functions: it is for practical mastery of foreign languages serves as a language and culture learning tool, information and educational activity is a tool and a means of self-education.

Thus, when speaking, students convey or explain information, they should be able to approve or condemn, convince, prove. Quickly correct students' own and others' thoughts in writing ability is required; writing from reading, processing material; the plan of the speech or writing theses. Students read newspaper and magazine articles, on average the ability to quickly read a complex work of art is important. Listening the ability to understand speech at a normal pace in live communication, as well as the meaning of television / radio programs is required.

Conventionally, students are instructed to focus on language knowledge, vocabulary, and the structure of a passage while reading. However, since reading comprehension is an interactive process, teachers can encourage learners to be active while reading a text. To help learners become critical and strategic readers, teachers can encourage them to ask questions and find the answers to the questions posed. Traditionally, the questioner is the teacher and the student only provides the answer. That is why many students are not able to generate good questions. However, generating questions has been proven a helpful reading strategy and students should engage in such behaviors to ensure that they have read the text carefully. Doing so leads them to a higher level of thinking and reflection upon their own learning.

The new educational paradigm defines the learners not only as receivers, but as ones who intensively process and interpret incoming information; develop cognitive skills and require individual control and self-regulation of learning. The presented study proves the possibility of students to progress in learning by integrating the academic work in the field of foreign language skills and chemical technology

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disciplines. Specific data for the advancement in both disciplines are a landmark for the possibilities of experimental learning and how it should be applied and developed.

REFERENCES:

1.Nosirova D.READING, LISTENING, WRITING AND ADVANTAGES OF SPEAKING.Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. Volume 2 issue 7

2. Rayimova M.DEVELOPMENT OF READING SKILLS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING PROCESS.SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS.Volume 3. Issue 1

3.Kontseptsiia razvitiia inoiazychnoho obrazovaniia [The concept of development of foreign language education]. (2008). Vestnik KazUMOiMY imeni Abylai khana — Bulletin of Kazakh Ablai khan university of international relations and world languages, 2(98), 20–22 [in Russian].

4.Nabiev A.Eshbayeva Z. Shokirova M.The Role of a New Generation of Textbooks in the Introduction of Competence Approach to the Education System(On the example of disciplines “Strength of materials” and “Technical Mechanics”).International Journal of Social Science Research and Review.2022.

5. Alavutdinova, N., & Ergasheva, L. (2024). COMMUNICATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF TEACHING THE UZBEK LANGUAGE AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. Science and innovation, 3(B1), 29-34.

6.Kadamzhanovna, A.N.(2023). ORIENTALISMS IN THE WORKS OF GAFUR GULAM (BY THE MATERIAL OF THE STORY" MISCLE"). Open Access Repository 4 (03), 63-67

7.Z Madraximova,Z & Ablaeva, N.(2022).CHARACTERISTICS OF LERMONTOV'S WORKS" HERO OF OUR TIME". Science and Innovation 1 (8), 1843-1845 2022

8.Madraximova,Z & Ablaeva, N. (2022)ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯ ЛЕРМОНТОВА" ГЕРОЙ НАШЕГО ВРЕМЕНИ".Science and innovation 1 (B8), 1843-1845 2022

9.Аблаева, Н.К.(2022).Сопоставительный анализ русских и узбекских пословиц. Та’лим fidoiyilari 6 (7), 687-691

10.Madraximova Zebo. (2023). DEATH GLORY OF THE WRITER. JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING, 2(5), 104–106.

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF 2024 = 5.073/Volume-2, Issue-5

11. Тоштемирова М.Ж., Урманова Г.У., Асраров М.И. Изучение действия инсектицида фозалона на функции митохондрий печени крыс в опытах in vivo/ Известия вузов. Химико-биологические науки.-2002.-N 4. - С. 28-31.

12. Pozilov M. K., Asrarov M. I., Urmanova G. U., Eshbakova K. A. Protective effect of salvifolin on liver mitochondrial function in rats with experimental diabetes. European Science Review, 2015, no. 7–8, pp. 3–7

13. Urmanova, G., & Yoldosheva, D. (2024). PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PULSE OXIMETRY. Theoretical Aspects in the Formation of Pedagogical Sciences, 3(5), 46–48.

14. Исломов, Ю., Каршиев, Д., Урманова, Г., & Исломов, А. (2023). Биологик актив бирикмаларни нурланишга таъсири. Актуальные вопросы детской хирургии, 1(1), 11–12

15. Urmanova, G., & Yo'ldosheva, D. (2023). TIBBIYOTNING RIVOJLANISHIGA HISSA QO'SHAYOTGAN AYRIM NOYOB USULLARNING KELIB CHIQISH TARIXI. Talqin Va Tadqiqotlar, 1(8).

16. Урманова, Г., & Абдусаломов, Ж. (2023). КОМПЬЮТАР ТОМОГРАФИЯ. Talqin Va Tadqiqotlar, 1(8).

17. Bekzodovna, J. M., & Akbarovna, D. G. (2023). INNOVATIVE METHODS AND TOOLS IN HIGHER EDUCATION. Science and Innovation, 2(11), 708-715.

18. Jumayeva, M. B., & Usmanovna, S. M. (2022). PRACTICAL METHODS OF CULTURE-BASED LANGUAGE TEACHING IN ENGLISH CLASSES. Science and innovation, 1(Special Issue 2), 612-615.

19. qizi To'yeva, M. S. (2022, November). YANGI O'ZBEKISTON ORIFA AYOLLARI VA G'ARB AYOLLARINING JAMIYATDAGI MAVQEYI VA ULARNING HUQUQLARI. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES (Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 74-81).

20. Бахранова, М., & Урманова, Г. (2023). Изучение физических характеристик ультразвука. Перспективы развития медицины, 1(1), 173.

21. Sharipova, S. (2023). THE ROLE OF COACHING TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE THINKING AND ABILITIES OF ADULTS IN LANGUAGE LEARNING PROCESS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 2(13), 5-12.

